

Review of Loren Goldman's The Principle of Political Hope

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REVIEWS

Loren Goldman's book *The Principle of Political Hope* addresses the question of how to sustain political hope amid uncertainty, crises, and failing democratic institutions. Goldman seeks to answer it by turning to five modern philosophers concerned with hope: Kant, Bloch, Peirce, James, and Dewey. The book's central thesis is that hope is not a passive emotion, but a vital and active principle necessary for democratic experimentation and collective action. Bridging German Idealism and American pragmatism, Goldman's understanding of hope opposes both the idea of history as progress, which equates hope with optimism, and the danger of presentism, nostalgia, melancholy, and resignation he finds in contemporary critiques of the concept of progress. Instead, he presents hope as a moral and political principle that acknowledges uncertainty and demands active participation. Goldman offers a helpful heuristic to structure the discussion by distinguishing a subjective and objective account of hope. While for Goldman, Kant and James lean toward the subjective, psychological side, Pierce and Bloch lean toward the objective, metaphysical side; Dewey transcends this dualism.

Goldman begins by examining hope in Kant's philosophy. While Kant's first Critique addresses what exists and his second Critique what ought to exist, his third Critique (and other shorter writings) explore "what we may hope for." Kant's concern is the "permissibility" of hope, aiming to distinguish between reasonable hope that is essential for morality, and hope that devolves into wishful thinking. As Goldman puts it, Kant navigates the relationship between the boundaries of human rationality and moral psychology (21).

Goldman locates the problem of hope in Kant's conception of practical belief, where hope is seen as a stance rooted in moral necessity rather than scientific evidence (21). For Kant, hope is thus not passive, but requires active engagement, with human conduct enabling the anticipation of a better world(60). Goldman links this practical hope to the idea of progress, claiming that a "weak, regulative" teleological understanding of history is Kant's way of reinforcing human autonomy as an ideal to strive for (60).

Kant's account of hope, however, has "a Munchausenian air" for Goldman, where one might force hope into possibility through sheer determination, despite contrary evidence. He argues that Kant's epistemological restrictions make him resist empirical assessments of hope, making it difficult to translate hope into collective political action (59). The break between freedom and nature, which hope aims to bridge, remains unresolved in Kant's work (60).

In the second chapter, Goldman introduces the Hegelian Marxist thinker Ernst Bloch as a counterpoint to Kant's subject-centered account of hope, emphasizing Bloch's idiosyncratic materialism combining Marx, Hegel, and Neo-Aristotelianism with a utopian twist. In focusing on Bloch's materialism, Goldman seeks to correct the (anglophone) image of Bloch as only a philosopher of aesthetics, explaining his materialist ontology of "layers of possibility" and tendencies (82). In Goldman's reading, Bloch however remains stuck in a sort of Hegelian determinism, albeit with matter and not spirit unfolding in world history, leaving little space for human agency (83). Below, we will raise some questions about this interpretation.

In the third chapter, Goldman turns to the pragmatists, starting with Peirce and James. His reading of pragmatism centers on three aspects: its Kantian roots, action-based belief, and evolutionary drive (87). Goldman shows how Peirce emphasizes scientific inquiry and the search for truth, driven by "logical hope" (92), presupposing that progress in knowledge is possible through collective reasoning and experimentation. Hope, therefore, is not merely a subjective feeling, but a logical necessity for sustaining inquiry in the face of uncertainty. According to Goldman, Peirce provides a second dimension of hope, namely "evolutionary hope" (98). By paralleling the logically good with the morally good (99), Peirce envisions the universe as evolving toward greater states of love and complexity—a process he refers to as "agapism" (evolution through love). However, Goldman criticizes Peirce's model as being metaphysical, arguing that Peirce's cosmic hope lacks relevance for immediate political action.

Goldman then contrasts Peirce's with that of James, who adds a subjective, psychological dimension to hope, focusing on individual belief and the will to act amid uncertainty—a perspective Goldman describes as the "will to hope" (103). For James, hope actively shapes personal and political engagement. Both philosophers reject linear progress but embrace the transformative potential of action and experimentation. Goldman, however, criticizes them for failing to connect hope to collective political action, leaving a gap between individual aspiration and societal possibilities (116).

Goldman's analysis culminates with Dewey, whom he considers the most political of the pragmatists. Dewey understands democracy as a morally ideal way of life rather than merely a political system. In Goldman's reading, Dewey

makes a qualitative leap beyond the other thinkers by bridging the dualism between subjective and objective sources of hope, emphasizing their reciprocal relationship in (political) practice or experience between “will and world” (123). Dewey’s understanding of democratic hope as “intelligent public practice” effectively attends to both poles. Dewey overcomes the dualism by assuming a mutually constituted relationship between the members of society and its socially constructed institutions (121). Transformation can only occur when both change.

By linking hope to Dewey’s emphatic and broad understanding of democracy and action, Goldman suggests that democratic hope is more than achieving political goals through democratic means. He argues that Dewey corrects this view by emphasizing the synergy of the regulative idea of democracy with intelligent experimental practices (120). For Dewey, democratic hope is grounded in the possibility of transforming society through collective intelligence and action, which he conceives of as social reconstruction (122). Reconstruction can be understood as an intelligent process of social transformation through education and political engagement which in turn restructures the social conditions for intelligence. This reconstruction can only be achieved through experimentation, the method of hope (153). In this context, Dewey advocates for reconstructing capitalist private property due to its impact on social power seeking to achieve a democratic world (145). Democracy offers the greatest potential for human growth and problem-solving because it encourages constant interaction between individuals and their environment, making it uniquely adaptable to change (133).

Goldman’s attempt to steer the argument toward Dewey as the “solution” to a supposed rift between “subjective” and “objective” philosophies of hope has heuristic merit, but also leads him to both overlook aspects of Bloch’s philosophy and leave the more immanent connections between the five thinkers somewhat underdeveloped. While Goldman’s effort to bring Bloch’s materialism in conversation with Dewey’s pragmatism is laudable, two criticisms arise with regard to Bloch. The first is that Goldman reads Bloch’s concept of “tendency” in a quasi-deterministic, strongly teleological sense, arguing that in Bloch’s materialism individuals are not much more than participants in nature’s broader intent (83). While there is indeed a tension between the “subjective” and “objective factor” in Bloch, Goldman seems to overlook Bloch’s attention to such aspects as the possible disappointment of hopes, the melancholy inherent in fulfillment, and, generally, his steadfast emphasis on the “subjective factor.”

Goldman’s deterministic reading appears to make him misjudge Bloch’s political utopianism. Contrary to his verdict that for Bloch socialism was “history’s unavoidable conclusion” (82) (part of a quote by Sombart and not Bloch’s own position), Bloch emphasizes that socialism was only a necessary, not a

sufficient condition for utopia (which remains a regulative ideal) and that it can indeed fail. Goldman's ensuing claim that Bloch seems to reject any hopes not aligning with dialectical materialism (85) does not convince. Bloch differentiates between hope in a conceptual sense and "educated hope" in a normative sense, acknowledging the power of non-dialectical-materialist hopes, for instance, when analyzing fascist imaginaries in *Heritage of Our Times*.

This leads to our second criticism concerning Goldman's treatment of *The Principle of Hope*. He overlooks what would appear to be a key chapter in Bloch for discussing hope: Chapter 13, where Bloch defines hope as an "expectant emotion." Goldman seems to conflate Bloch's concepts of hope and utopia, leaving the psychological aspect of Bloch's work unexplored. Eventually, his deterministic interpretation of Bloch prevents him from recognizing potential connections between Bloch's and Dewey's experimentalism, missing an opportunity for an intriguing comparison.

Notwithstanding the problems in his interpretation of Bloch, Goldman's meticulous yet accessible interpretations of hope in Kant and Dewey, Peirce, and James make the book a valuable contribution to the study of the philosophy of hope. For anyone looking for a deep dive into these philosophers' understandings of hope, *The Principle of Political Hope* is a great resource.